

Kinetics of Thermal Dehydration of Zirconium and Thorium Hydroxide Hydrogels

N. K. MITRA and S. SINHAMAHAPATRA

Department of Applied Chemistry, University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700 009

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Kinetics of thermal dehydration of synthetic zirconium and thorium hydroxide hydrogels have been studied by thermogravimetric method. Dehydration followed first order kinetics upto a certain stage. The rate constants for the initial and final stages of dehydration were related to the water content of the gels. Textural change on heat treatment also contributes to it.

HYDROGELS are generally two phase systems consisting of a solid and a liquid and they generally behave as elastic solids. The kinetic approach to the study of thermal decomposition of many hydrated materials is important not only because the economic utilisation of many of them depends on the rates of reaction but also kinetic studies in addition give basic information about the materials, their structure, surfaces and so forth. Water is an integral part of the gel structure. Subba Rao *et al*¹ studied the thermal decomposition of zirconyl oxalate and found that it proceeded in two steps. An excellent review of the kinetic processes has been given by Garner² who has classified reactions into two categories, exothermic or endothermic. Whiting and Turner³ found that the rate of decomposition was influenced by grain size and surface area.

The effect of vapour pressure has also been investigated by a number of authors⁴⁻⁶ and they explained the early stage of dehydration as due to the formation of narrow capillaries within the structure.

Mitra *et al*⁷ found that the rate constant during zeolitic dehydration followed an inverse relationship with the total water content and they explained this in terms of structuredness of water molecules in the lattice. They have also shown that the activation energy was independent of particle size in aluminosilicate gel structure.

In the present investigation kinetics of thermal dehydration of two important hydroxide hydrogels of Zr⁴⁺ and Th⁴⁺ was undertaken.

Experimental

Hydrogels of zirconium and thorium were prepared from acidic solutions of zirconium nitrate and thorium nitrate by interaction with NH₄Cl-NH₄OH buffer at pH 9. After proper ageing they were processed in accordance with the reported method⁹ to get rid of extraneous impurities. The kinetics of the dehydration process was studied by TG method⁸.

Results and Discussion

Both the hydrogels were prepared under identical condition and incubated properly at a temperature of 32±1°. The DTGA curves showed endothermic peaks in both the cases and the temperatures for studying the kinetics of dehydration were selected accordingly. The isothermal dehydration curves (not reproduced) showed exponential behaviour and as such first order kinetics was suggested. The method of Guggenheim as used by Mitra *et al*⁸ was adopted to calculate initial water concentration L_∞ which can be dehydrated at the experimental temperature and also the rate constant K₁ for the initial stage of dehydration using the following equation :

$$\log \Delta L = \frac{-K_1 t}{2.303} + \log L_\infty [1 - \exp(-K_1 \Delta t)] \dots (1)$$

where ΔL is the difference between the mass loss at time $t + \Delta t$, and time t , the time interval Δt between the two sets of readings being kept fixed at a value greater than twice the time for 50% dehydration. Using equation (1) the rate constant was calculated from the slope of linear plot obtained by plotting $\log \Delta L$ against t . Knowing Δt , and having obtained K₁ from the slope, L_∞ was determined from the intercept on the log axis. Figs. 1 and 2 show the Guggenheim plots and the value of K₁ and L_∞ are recorded in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The acti-

Fig. 1. ΔL Plots of zirconium hydroxide hydrogel at different temperature.

 Fig. 2. ΔL Plots of thorium hydroxide hydrogel at different temperature.

Fig. 4. Isothermal dehydration curves for zirconium and thorium hydroxide hydrogels at different temperature.

 TABLE 1—VALUES OF RATE CONSTANTS (K_1) AS DETERMINED FROM LOG ΔL VS TIME PLOTS

Hydrogel	K_1 (min^{-1}) at $^{\circ}\text{C}$			
	100	130	160	190
Zirconium hydroxide	0.1151	0.1842	0.2072	0.2533
Thorium hydroxide	0.1151	0.2303	0.2993	0.3915

 TABLE 2—VALUES OF L_{∞} AS DETERMINED FROM GUGGENHEIM EQUATION (Initial weight of the sample 0.5 g)

Hydrogel	L_{∞} (g) at $^{\circ}\text{C}$			
	100	130	160	190
Zirconium hydroxide	0.0522	0.0651	0.0755	0.0841
Thorium hydroxide	0.0361	0.0465	0.0543	0.0577

vation energy was calculated from the usual Arrhenius plots using the rate constants (Figs. 3 and 5).

Fig. 3. Arrhenius plots of hydrogels for the initial stage of dehydration.

Fig. 5. Arrhenius plots of hydrogels for the final stage of dehydration.

Gel water is normally characterised by loose bonding with which it is attached to the framework. Most of the non-crystalline hydrogels contain colloidal water which may be regarded as the extreme case of broken bond water in which the particle size of the solid to which the water is linked is extremely small. The unsaturated surface charges on the crystallites are numerous and able to influence not only the water molecules which are in contact with the surface but also some at a small distance. The temperature range for studying the dehydration kinetics was ascertained from the DIGA curves where the peak temperature was found to be 150° for zirconium and 155° for thorium hydroxide gels, respectively.

Surface area is one of the important parameters upon which the rate of solid state reaction depends. In the present investigation the sample size was kept fixed at $-20+50$ mesh (B. S. S.) for both the hydrogels.

Although L_{∞} values differed, the magnitude of rate constants remained the same at 100° . Above this temperature the rate constant values followed a direct relationship to the total water content of

the samples which has been clearly revealed through the results in Tables 1 and 2. Again, both K_1 and L_α values were found to be a direct function of temperature which means that the reaction rate and the amount of water expelled from the gel increased with increase in temperature of heat treatment.

From the nature of the log $[(L_\alpha - L)/L_\alpha]$ vs time curves (Fig. 4) it was clearly evident that the whole course of the reaction did not follow the first order kinetics. As such, the limits of applicability of the first order law have been determined from the extent of linearity of these plots (Fig. 4).

TABLE 3—EXTENT OF VALIDITY OF FIRST ORDER LAW AS DETERMINED FROM LOG $[(L_\alpha - L)/L_\alpha]$ VS TIME PLOTS

Hydrogel	First order law as valid upto % dehydration at °C			
	100	130	160	190
Zirconium hydroxide	58.31	61.98	64.52	81.38
Thorium hydroxide	63.69	74.08	74.88	77.61

Thus it appears that with an increase in temperature the magnitudes of validity of first order law increased. This means that more water from the gel lattice was expelled by the same mechanism. Though the rate of the dehydration process is solely dependent on the nature of the residual dehydrated phase, the effect of temperature may be explained in the way that the OH groups and water molecules get activated by thermal vibrations.

The rate constant, K_2 , for the final stage of dehydration was calculated from the equation

$$K_2 = \frac{dL/dt}{(L_\alpha - L)}$$

where dL/dt is the slope of the weight loss against time (curves not reproduced) at a point of 80% dehydration and L is the actual loss at this time. The point at 80% dehydration was considered in this case because it appears that upto this point the rate of dehydration followed first order kinetics. The calculated values of K_2 are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF RATE CONSTANT FOR THE SECOND STAGE (K_2) OF DEHYDRATION

Hydrogel	K_2 (min ⁻¹) at °C			
	100	130	160	190
Zirconium hydroxide	0.0851	0.1442	0.1681	0.2182
Thorium hydroxide	0.0851	0.1812	0.2456	0.3086

The K_2 values followed the same sequence with respect to the two hydrogels as observed for K_1 values. K_2 values were always lower than the K_1 values indicating slower rate of dehydration. This might be due to the fact that after the initial stage

of dehydration, when a significant amount of water has been expelled, the residual water concentration was so low that the interaction of these structurally isolated water molecules face greater barrier and as such the rate constant values decreased.

The calculated values of activation energy from Arrhenius plot have been represented in Table 5.

TABLE 5—VALUES OF ACTIVATION ENERGIES FOR INITIAL AND FINAL STAGES OF DEHYDRATION

Hydrogel	Activation energy (kcal/mole)	
	Initial stage of dehydration	Final stage of dehydration
Zirconium hydroxide	3.20	3.66
Thorium hydroxide	2.29	4.80

In both the cases the activation energy values in the initial stage of dehydration was significantly low which was in fair agreement with the statement made for comparing the reaction rate constants. On examining the values of the individual hydroxide, it was found that the activation energy value of zirconium hydroxide hydrogel was greater than that of thorium hydroxide hydrogel. It is to be mentioned that the activation energy for the initial stage of dehydration followed a direct relationship with the L_α values for this type of gel dehydration as will be revealed from Table 6.

TABLE 6—RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN L_α VALUES AND ACTIVATION ENERGY AT THE INITIAL STAGE OF DEHYDRATION

Hydrogel	L_α values (g)	Activation energy kcal/mole
Zirconium hydroxide	0.0841	3.20
Thorium hydroxide	0.0577	2.29

But this relationship gets reversed at the final stage of dehydration (Tables 2 and 5). Because of its higher atomic weight, the structural flexibility of thorium was comparatively low and as such the textural change on dehydration was not comparable to that of the hydrogel containing zirconium.

Conclusion :

(i) Maximum portion of the dehydration of hydroxides of Zr^{4+} and Th^{4+} followed first order kinetics.

(ii) Dehydration proceeded in two steps and the rate at the final stage was slower.

(iii) Activation energy followed a direct relationship with the water content at the initial stage of dehydration.

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References

1. M. SUBBA RAO, T. GANGADEVI and R. NARAYANAN KUTTY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, **19A**, 303.
2. W. E. GARNER, "Chemistry of the Solid State", Butterworths Scientific Publications, London, 1955, p. 213.
3. G. H. WHITING and W. E. S. TURNER, *J. Soc. Glass Technol.*, 1930, **14**, 409.
4. C. C. FURANS, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1931, **23**, 584.
5. P. MURRAY and J. WHITE, *Trans. Brit. Ceram. Soc.*, 1955, **54**, 151.
6. W. E. GARNER and M. G. TANNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 47.
7. N. K. MITRA, S. GHATAK and S. MITRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, **19A**, 195.
8. N. K. MITRA, K. L. ROY and S. MITRA, *Trans. Brit. Ceram. Soc.*, 1975, **74**, 263.
9. N. K. MITRA and K. L. ROY, *Trans. Indian Ceram. Soc.*, 1972, **31**, 82.